

The Subject-Event Approach to Modeling Complex Systems

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Preface

This article was originally written in Russian in 2015 as the first conceptual outline of the Subject-Event Approach. It lays the philosophical groundwork for the ideas that have since been formally developed and implemented.

The formal specification of this approach, the BSL language, and the 'boldsea-engine' architecture are detailed in the 2025 paper: Executable Ontologies: Synthesizing Event Semantics with Dataflow Architecture <https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.09775>

Thing (Object) Ontology

The traditional way of thinking for modern humans—in everyday life, in science, and in philosophy—is *thing-based* (or *object-based*) thinking, which is characterized by describing the world as a set of spatially localized objects or things. Things themselves are defined through a collection of predicates. The relationships between objects are described through relations and classifications, formally captured in tables and graphs. Modern methods for describing/modeling complex systems adhere to this thing-based ontology: first, decomposition—identifying objects—then their classification, ascribing properties to them, and establishing relations between them ("part-whole," "genus-species," "depends on," etc.).

Event Ontology

However, in philosophy, besides the traditional thing-based ontology, another approach to describing the world is known, though not as widespread: the *event-based* one. Ludwig Wittgenstein adhered to an event-based view at the level of logical, linguistic systems. At the beginning of his famous "Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus," he stated: "The world is the

totality of facts, not of things.... What is happening, the fact—is the existence of co-events [so-bytiy]." A radically extreme event-based approach, at the level of ontology's foundations, was first proposed by Bertrand Russell, who stated: "the world consists of a certain number, possibly finite, possibly infinite, of entities... Each of these entities can be called an 'event'."

Yes, we can describe, say, a biological organism as a spatial structure of molecules. But, on the other hand, we can also represent it as a system of events of chemical interactions between these molecules, distributed over a certain period of time. In this case, it's clear that the event-based description will give us a more complete understanding of the organism compared to a purely structural analysis. Moving further into the nature of things, molecules can also be described not as "balls on sticks," but as a collection of events of atomic interactions—it's clear that the structure, the spatial position of the molecule's elements, is secondary to the events of electron exchanges. And atoms themselves should be described as systems of acts-events of particle interactions. Ultimately, Russell, analyzing the quantum theory of matter, concludes: "matter is just a convenient way of grouping events." And to the legitimate question, "events of *what?* events happening *to what?*" he replies: "events that simply happen, and do not happen 'to' matter or 'to' anything else."

The Computer Analogy

A computer analogy can help us understand the essence of event ontology. What is the "world" of a computer at the elementary (processor) level? A continuous stream of simple events: 0100100100010010010... And nothing more. But at another level—the interface level—some sequences of this stream appear as fully-fledged things: interface elements, letters, game characters. Each "thing" shown to us on the screen corresponds to a certain, not necessarily continuous, sequence of the processor event stream (ones and zeros). And what do we do when we want to change these things? That's right, we add new events to the original stream.

So, we have only events: systems of events and events of changing systems of events, from which new things can be formed at the interface level. Let's specifically note: there are no things at the elementary stream level—they only arise when templates are applied to this stream. Which, by the way, are themselves time-distributed structures of events from this same stream, since there is nothing else in the computer's world.

From this philosophical introduction, we should take away a simple idea: our world can be viewed both as a set of things and as a stream of events, where things are defined through sets of these events.

Event-based Description of Complex Systems

Certainly, when we turn to applied problems of describing a complex system, say, a large modern enterprise, we shouldn't be concerned with the deep (at the level of elementary particle interactions) event ontology of every single bolt. We should be primarily interested in the bolt's participation in the system's functioning, i.e., the events: "delivered to warehouse," "brought to assembly point," "screwed in." And not just the fact of participation, but its content, describing the properties that were essential for each event.

For example, for the event "brought to assembly point," the bolt's weight is important—is a cart needed, or can a box of bolts be carried in a pocket. The event "screwed in" is feasible if the bolt's thread matches the part's thread. And so, if we record all the events in which the bolt participated, we will get its complete description. Not an abstract one, but a concrete and exhaustive description of how the bolt "looks" to this specific system, what properties it has, and when and how it participates in the system's functioning. If there is no event recording the bolt's color, then the description of the bolt (for this system) will not include the property "color."

Thus, by using the proposed event-based approach—that is, by recording all events in which objects appeared, were measured, moved, used, changed, etc.—we get a complete description of these objects within the analyzed system.

At first glance, it might seem this is just a form of accounting, a way to optimize the recording of object parameters. However, let's consider what lies behind the seemingly simple phrase "recording an event." Take, for example, the event "screwed in a bolt." It's important to note that this event involves not just the bolt (A), but also other objects like the parts being joined (B and C) and a subject (S) who performs this event. (A clarification is necessary here: we are not talking about the act, the procedure, or the action, but specifically about the event "screwed in a bolt," i.e., *recording the fact* that the result was achieved.) That is, our full event should be named: "subject S joined parts B and C with bolt A." This means that the record of each system event contains not only information about the objects involved

but also data about their relationships (objects A, B, and C form a whole D from the moment of the event) plus a description of the subject (S produced object D).

Therefore, recording all events realized in a complex system should give us an exhaustive (within this system) description of every object, every subject, and their relationships. In essence, the resulting event stream contains complete information about the system.

Principle of Event Identification

It's clear that for analyzing the functioning of a complex system, say, the same enterprise, there's no need to record every event at the level of technological processes. For instance, the screwing of a bolt by a specific subject should be represented in the event stream by two events: "receiving A, B, and C" and "handing over part D," rather than by events for each turn of the wrench. We can specify the following formal conditions that determine the necessity and sufficiency of including an event in the event stream:

1. The event is performed or registered by one of the system's subjects;
2. The event is performed on one of the system's objects;
3. The fact of the event's occurrence (or absence) is a condition for the performance of an event by another subject, or by the same subject but with a different object.

From these conditions, it follows that an event is defined by specifying the *object(s)* it happens to and the *subject* that performed or registered it. The subject can be a specific person, a role, a team, as well as software agents, sensors, etc. Events that affect the system's behavior but are not linked to any of its subjects should be attributed to an absolute subject. It is precisely because any event in the system is such only on the condition of its connection to a specific subject that this approach is called not just "event-based," but "*subject-event*"

Principle of Unification

The most important and interesting aspect of the subject-event approach is the *principle of unifying descriptions: all subjects and all objects within the enterprise are exhaustively described as sets of events*. If we extract from the system's event stream all events performed by a certain subject, including their filling out every field of an application form when hired, we get a complete description of that subject. And, analogously, if we collect all events

generated by all subjects regarding a certain object (events of recording properties, changing properties, inclusion in other objects), we get an exhaustive description of the object—specifically as an object *in this complex system*.

To maintain uniformity of description, the initial ascription of properties to an object must also be recorded as an event, attributed to the past, say, to the moment the object was introduced into the system (delivery of materials, equipment, a new order, etc.). Such events are attributed to the absolute subject. That is, in the event-based approach, any statement about any object is framed as a statement about an event, recorded or initiated by a specific subject.

What has been said about objects within the event-based approach can also be formulated in terms of data: *in the subject-event approach, all data is generated by events and recorded as events*. Data can either enter the system (incoming resources, order conditions) or be generated within the system (modification of resources)—in any case, it is described as an event of ascribing a predicate to an object, performed by a specific subject.

Thus, in the subject-event approach, the primary and only element for describing systems is the event: the enterprise is represented as a stream of events, performed by subjects on objects, and the subjects and objects themselves are recorded in the system as sets of events related to them, most of which occur during the enterprise's operation, and some of which are recorded at the time of the objects' and subjects' inclusion in the system.

Principle of Relativity

The proposed principle of recording subjects and objects (as sets of events) eliminates the absolutization of their description, which is characteristic of the thing-based approach. Each object is included in a subject's actions with the set of parameters that are discernible in that action (clearly, the object "bolt" has different descriptions for a worker, an engineer, and an accountant, and for the director, it doesn't exist at all). Similarly, relationships between subjects are recorded only to the extent that their event sets overlap: subjects are linked to the same object, included in the same action.

It is also clear that the change of an object's state is relative and subject-dependent. If a subject did not discern an event of change (or this change is insignificant for them, for

example, fixing a typo in a brochure is not an event for a designer), then for that subject, the object has not changed its state.

The event-based approach resolves the problem of unambiguous classification of objects: resources, artifacts, documents, products, etc. Since all objects discernible by subjects are conceived as sets of events, there is no need for absolute, fixed typing: depending on the subject's level and role, different subsets can be extracted from the general set of events related to an object, which will be recorded as different types—for example, as a product, a document, or even trash (for a cleaner).

This principle of relativity in defining objects and subjects is important for unifying and minimizing descriptions, as well as for optimizing the relationships between subjects and objects. And most importantly, it allows for producing and analyzing many substantially non-coinciding, yet consistent at the lowest level (the event stream level), descriptions of the system, made from the perspectives of various subjects.

Registration of the Event Stream

In the initial stage of system modeling, registering the event stream is possible by compiling lists of all events associated with each subject, as well as by analyzing changes to objects. Ultimately, the arrays of events identified by these registration methods should coincide. A discrepancy should be seen as an indication of organizational problems: meaningless events that have no consequences, or events whose performance is not strictly assigned to a specific subject.

With a sufficient level of informational support in the enterprise, events can be recorded automatically by parsing the subjects' activities.

Comparison of the Subject-Event Approach with Existing BPM Systems

The method of analysis and data recording described above is primarily intended for modeling business systems. The closest in name and, of course, in content to the proposed subject-event approach are two methods for describing business systems: EPC diagrams (event-driven process chain) and the subject-oriented approach (s-BPM) from Metasonic. Let's try to conduct a comparative analysis of these enterprise modeling methods.

EPC Diagrams

The subject-event approach diverges from EPC at the very definition of an "event." In EPC, an event is considered a state, recorded at the input or output of a function and defined by a set of specific parameters at a certain moment in time. Although this definition seems quite intuitive, in the general case, it contains a large element of ambiguity: the state of *what*? The entire system? A certain object? A subject? On the other hand, many events that clearly influence the business process do not fall under this definition: EPC includes logical connectors, logical interdependencies, information flows, and other elements that are not described as events, although, in essence, they are. This ambiguity is completely eliminated in the subject-event approach thanks to the unification of descriptions of all entities in the system—any of them is recorded as a set of events.

A significant advantage of the subject-event approach is the elimination of multiple types of connections in modeling (control flow, message flow, logical links, associations, etc.)—all connections are viewed exclusively as causal (logical) links between events. Of course, one chain of linked events can be labeled as a resource change process, another as a management process, a third as the performance of a function by a subject, but in the initial record, all these processes are nothing more than streams of standardly described events, linked by execution conditions.

Thus, from the perspective of the subject-event approach, EPC diagrams should be seen as a convenient and visual form of representing a fragment of the enterprise's activity, reflecting the sequence of a series of functions performed by one or more single-level subjects. The existing diagrams can serve as a data source for forming the enterprise's event stream.

Subject-Oriented Approach (s-BPM)

From the perspective of the evolution of business process modeling tools, the subject-event approach should be seen as the next step after s-BPM. While retaining all the latter's advantages, the subject-event approach has the important advantage of unifying subject and object descriptions. This ensures the closest possible convergence of three aspects of the enterprise's functioning: (1) direct activity, (2) its modeling, and (3) data operations. The event stream simultaneously records, in one format, both the enterprise's structure (the

relationships between all its elements) and the complete description of all elements (both subjects and objects).

The foundation of s-BPM consists of acts (events) of relationships between subjects, to which the enterprise's functioning is reduced, or more accurately, onto which its activity is projected. Moving further in this direction, the subject-event approach proposes considering *any act of a subject* as a meaningful element of the system, all its relationships with both subjects and objects, i.e., any event capable of influencing the future state of the enterprise.

The principle of describing the enterprise in s-BPM and in the subject-event approach is similar — a set of subjects is taken, and their relationships are recorded — but in the event-based approach, the subject is not seen as a system-forming factor. The subject is not pre-defined for the description: like any object, it "emerges," revealed during the formation of the event stream as a certain set of events. The main question in the event-based approach is not "what does this subject do?" but "which subject performs this event and with what object?" Attention shifts from the subject to the event, making the latter the fundamental invariant: a few human-subjects can be combined into one subject, or, conversely, one subject can be split into several, or even replaced by a software agent, and the object (resource) can also be changed to another — and the event itself will remain the same. That is, the very description of the enterprise through a stream of events is maximally adapted for modification and optimization, without changing the principles of data organization or their description formats.

In response to the "description of a process with only five symbols" principle, put forward by s-BPM, the subject-event approach offers its own: "description of everything with one symbol." This principle stems from understanding the enterprise-organism as a stream of events: *if we record all events — we get a complete description of the entire system*. And no additional entities.

Although, of course, "one symbol" is just a slogan. The event stream of an enterprise cannot itself be represented as a *finite model*, as a logically separate schema with a fixed notation. The event stream should be understood as a multidimensional universe of events, which for analysis must be viewed from a specific perspective, projected onto a certain plane. For instance, if we isolate events at the "subject-subject" relationship level, we get a subject-oriented description (s-BPM). If we record the start and end events of a series of

functions, we'll have an EPC-like image of a system fragment. That is, from the event-based perspective, any existing business process description scheme should be seen as a visualization method, as a projection of the enterprise-organism onto one of the possible semantic planes. And there can be an infinite number of such projections.

A significant advantage of the subject-event approach is that it doesn't propose some new schema, an original model, but rather states that all existing schemas can, on one hand, be reduced to the event stream, and on the other, be automatically extracted from it by fixing certain parameters, for example, the subject level, the movement of a particular resource, and so on.

Conclusions

Let's briefly repeat the main principles of the subject-event approach:

1. Unification of description at the lowest level: only events exist; everything else—subjects, objects (resources, documents)—is described as sets of events;
2. Merging of model and data: the event stream contains complete information about the system (description of objects and subjects, system structure);
3. Achievement of relativity in description: any object exists only for a specified subject, described through the set of events discernible by that subject;
4. Formalization of the description level: subjects that discern the same objects are attributed to the same level; the description possesses integrity at each level;
5. Consistency of descriptions at the highest level: all possible models (structural, functional, etc.) are reduced to their common stream of elementary events.

In essence, the subject-event approach is not a method of organization, management, modernization, or optimization, but only a universal platform for describing complex systems with time-distributed complexity. The choice of a particular management and optimization strategy can be proposed after a formal analysis of the system's event stream structure. But even the mere fact of an event-based description, without "hanging" any management or optimization strategies on it, gives us, on one hand, a tool for visualizing the system's work at any level and from any subject's point of view, and on the other, a formalization of all regulations and a tool for their rapid modification. After all, a regulation is nothing more than a list of events performed by a subject and conditionally linked to other events.

That is, one of the important advantages of the subject-event approach to analyzing complex systems is the initial separation of the ontological description from management and optimization methods. The system appears before us at several levels:

1. The lowest level of events, containing complete information about the system;
2. The level of objects and subjects (which are represented as sets of events);
3. The level of the hierarchy of event systems—processes, actions, activities, and their connection to objects and subjects;
4. The level of management and optimization, represented by schemas and models that display the enterprise's structure from various points of view.

Each level is ideologically and programmatically built upon the lower one as a structure of the latter's elements, but ontologically, all structures at all levels consist of elements from the lowest level (events) and can be reduced to it. That is, ontologically (and programmatically), events are not differentiated by level; they are all elements of the system's event stream.

It should be emphasized that the subject-event approach itself is merely a tool for describing complex systems and does not directly predetermine any methods for optimization and planning of enterprises. (Although the very act of modeling the system's event stream may reveal problems in its organization and suggest solutions.) However, it is this extremely unified and globally connected description that can be seen as the foundation for implementing and automating any optimization and planning methods in real-time.

References

1. Wittgenstein, L. (1961). *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*. (Trans. D.F. Pears & B.F. McGuinness). London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
2. Boldachev A. (2011). *Temporality and the Philosophy of Absolute Relativism*. – M.: Lenand. [in Russian].
3. Boldachev A. (2015). [Introduction to Temporal Ontology](#). *Who Makes Philosophy in Russia Today. Volume III* / Compiled by A. S. Nilogov. — M.: Sam Poligrafist LLC. [in Russian].
4. Russell, B. (1945). *A History of Western Philosophy*. New York: Simon & Schuster.